

Modeling mechanical properties of specific polycrystalline materials through simulation

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ABSTRACT

Simulation of mechanical properties of bulk materials based on microstructure and properties of single crystals is a promising tool for studying macromechanical plasticity characteristics of little-studied or under-designed materials. In particular, magnets based on MnBi, MnAlC can be produced by plastic deformation and the flow curves of the material are crucial in the design of such processes. The work focused on the study of the capabilities of NEPER and FEpX software and verification of the modelling results based on experimental data for α -phase Ti-6Al-4V. A satisfactory matching of the calculated stress-strain curves with the experiment was obtained for the number of 200 grains (uniform orientation distribution) per unit volume and number of elements of about 100k. A number of parameters of the crystal plasticity model showed a weak influence on the modelling results, which can be used to reduce the dimensions when searching for optimal solutions.

Motivation

The mechanical properties of polycrystals and creation of their models can be obtained in two ways - the direct way, by study of full-scale specimens with the use of phenomenological theory of elasticity, plasticity and deformability and the calculation way, based on simulation, using the properties of single crystals and their interaction with each other under the influence of external loads. The second method is more flexible and cost-effective, despite potential calculation errors. In the pursuit of optimal solutions, it is undoubtedly preferable. Today's software options, such as free software NEPER, FEpX enable the implementation of the phenomenological approach quite effectively. The main focus has been on examining the capabilities of FEpX and its underlying theoretical models. For polycrystalline materials the most important characteristic for modelling different forming processes is the stress-strain curves.

Research

Geometry preparation – NEPER [1]
Solver of mechanics – FEpX [2]

Strain rate – 0,01 1/s
Uniform crystal orientation distributions

Constitutive equations of crystal plasticity (used in FEpX)

$$\dot{\gamma}^k = \dot{\gamma}_0 \left(\frac{|\tau^k|}{g^k} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \text{sgn}(\tau^k)$$

$$g^k = \dot{\gamma} h_0 \left(\frac{g_s^k(\dot{\gamma}) - g_0^k}{g_s^k(\dot{\gamma}) - g_0^k} \right)$$

$$g_s^k(\dot{\gamma}) = g_{s0}^k \left(\frac{\dot{\gamma}}{\dot{\gamma}_{s0}} \right)^{m'}$$

Parameters of material (α -phase Ti-6Al-4V) [3]

C11, (GPa)	C12, (GPa)	C13, (GPa)	C44, (GPa)	g_{0basal} (MPa)	g_{0prism} (MPa)	g_{0pyram} (MPa)	h_0 (MPa)	g_{s0} (MPa)
169,7	88,7	61,7	42,5	390	468	663	190	530

weak influence on stress-strain curve

m	m'	$\dot{\gamma}_0$ (1/s)	$\dot{\gamma}_{s0}$ (1/s)
0,01	0,01	1,0	5e10

Simulation (with different settings) and experiment results

Optimal tessellation and mesh

Number of seeds - 200, 115k elem., Laguerre tessellation, id=1, 100x100x100 μm , uniaxial compression, true strain - 0,07; von-Mises stresses (MPa)

Experiment on uniaxial compression

Specimens with different degrees of deformation

Initial size - h=15 mm, d=10 mm, HV 3075 MPa, Tann = 920 °C 5h with a heating rate of 10 K/min, cooling rate of 0.43 K/min

Experimental and numerical determination of constants of phenomenological models

Conclusions

- For modelling the flow curve of a non-textured polycrystal, a reasonable number of grains for a unit volume is about 200 grains with uniform orientation. Reducing the grains to 50 grains shows a significant dependence of the curve on the number of grains. The number of tetragonal elements unit volume is rationally about 110..130k elem. Increasing it did not significantly change the modelled curves, but decreasing it to 50k and less showed a rather large dependence. Representative size of the elementary deformable cube can be estimated as $L \cong \sqrt[3]{200} \times L_{el}$, where L_{el} - average linear grain size, L - cube edge length.
- By modelling monotonic plastic deformation at low strain rates, which is typical for the most of the forming processes, the plasticity model of crystals can be reduced. In particular, fixed-state strain rate scaling, saturation strength rate scaling coefficient and power for titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V with hexagonal α -phase were found to have a weak influence on stress-strain curve.
- Using machine learning methods, it is rational to analyse flow curves and microstructure together for further estimation of single crystal parameters. The elastic constants may either be taken from experiments or ab-initio simulations. To produce rare-earth-free permanent magnets, such as MnBi or MnAlC [5], through hot deformation a thorough comprehension of their mechanical properties is crucial.

References

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